

DEVELOPMENT OF SAPPHIRE OPTICAL SENSOR FOR CERAMIC COMPOSITE CHARACTERIZATION

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ABSTRACT

Embedded fiber-optic sensors can be used for real-time monitoring of composite materials during processing and fabrication, installation and in-service. The present work is directed toward the development of an optical sapphire fiber sensor appropriate for high temperature applications. The sensor operates on the recently developed technique of spatial modulation induced within multimode optical fibers. The principle of operation of a sensor based on this technique, and the theoretical basis for spatial modulation in multimode optical fibers is discussed briefly. More importantly, direct experimental evidence of spatial modulation in sapphire optical waveguides, when lateral compression loads are applied to the fiber, is presented.

INTRODUCTION

Embedded fiber-optic sensors offer significant potential for application in composite materials. Optical fibers made of silica or polymer based materials are proposed as sensing elements for testing composite materials at low temperatures. However, at high temperatures (over 1000° C) silica and polymer optical fibers cannot be used as waveguides. For these high temperature environments, optical grade sapphire (aluminum oxide) fibers offer an alternative [1]. Sapphire fibers possess reasonably good optical properties, but are difficult to be made into single mode fibers. Most conventional high sensitive techniques are either based on phase modulation or polarization modulation and therefore require single mode fibers for propagation of coherent light. Since available sapphire fibers are multimode fibers, as opposed to single mode, these techniques are not suitable. For multimode fibers, an inexpensive and reasonably sensitive technique was developed recently [2]. The technique is based on spatial intensity modulation (SIM) induced within multimode optical fibers. The feasibility of using this technique with conventional optical fibers to characterize composite materials was demonstrated successfully [3].

Unlike silica or polymer fibers that are available commercially, optical grade sapphire fibers are unclad single crystal fibers. In order to be able to use these fibers as optical waveguides two coatings are necessary, a cladding layer and a protective jacket. A cladding layer is required to confine the optical signal propagating within the fiber core and limit attenuation and losses. In addition, an external protective coating is needed to protect the fiber from its surrounding environment. For thermal durability of the sapphire optical waveguide, alumina is the preferred cladding material. For the protective layer, silicon carbide is chosen due to its superior mechanical and thermal properties. The coating process and requirements were reported earlier [4].

The purpose of the present work is to apply the SM technique to sapphire optical waveguides and thus prove the feasibility of using these fibers in high temperature environment to

characterize composite materials. In the first section of the paper the theoretical basis for spatial modulation in multimode optical fibers and the sensor operating principles is discussed briefly. This is followed by experimental evidence of spatial modulation in sapphire optical waveguides when lateral compression loads are applied to the fiber.

SPATIAL MODULATION IN MULTIMODE OPTICAL FIBERS

Propagation of electromagnetic waves in multimode fibers is well known to be in the form of a finite number of guided modes that are responsible for a stable light pattern within the optical fiber [5]. The presence of any mechanical stresses or other forms of perturbation that changes the boundary conditions in the fiber, will lead to energy exchange between the modes, resulting in modal power redistribution. This energy exchange or coupling is referred to as spatial modulation, since it results in spatial variation of the light pattern within the fiber.

Comparative measurements of the distribution and subsequent redistribution of the modal power can be accomplished by scanning the far field pattern at the fiber end using a CCD camera or array of photodetectors. This technique can be employed as a sensitive mechanism for measuring perturbations induced by external mechanical stresses. The sensitivity of this type of fiber-optic sensor is related to the modal structure of the fiber and to the medium surrounding it. The launching conditions of the light determines the initial modal power distribution (MPD) and is the most critical factor for sensitivity. In order to improve the sensitivity of the device, it is preferred to excite higher order modes within the fiber. This is done by launching an optical beam slightly off-axis to the fiber. In this way, the far field pattern becomes totally dark at the center, and any induced power coupling from higher to lower order modes i.e., from the periphery to the center, can be detected easily. The quality of the fiber end faces and the fiber coating are additional factors that influence the level of sensitivity.

The possible changes in boundary conditions induced by mechanical stresses that leads to spatial modulation can be listed as, changes in refractive indices of the core and/or cladding, the geometry of the waveguide and the interaction length of the fiber with the mechanical stress. In principle, the coupled mode theory [6] can be employed for accurate analysis of the spatial modulation induced by the stress. In practice however, the coupled mode theory is too complicated to be used for multimode fibers, supporting a large number of guided modes..

For the special case of modal perturbation where an external load is applied along the length of the fiber for a known distance 'd', and the only change is in the refractive index of the cladding, a simplified approach is suggested [7]. For this physical situation, the device can be treated as a waveguide consisting of discontinuities at $z = 0$ and $z = d$, as shown in Fig. 1. The effect of the change in index is to redistribute the power between the various guided modes of the fiber. The output modal power distribution (region III) can be solved in terms of the input modal power distribution (region I) and changes in the boundary conditions in region II, by applying continuity equations at $z = 0$ and $z = d$,

$$\sum_{n=1}^N b_n e_n - \sum_{n=1}^N c_n e_n = \sum_{s=1}^S f_s E_s - \sum_{s=1}^S g_s E_s \quad \text{at } z = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\sum_{s=1}^S f_s E_s \exp(-j\alpha_s d) - \sum_{s=1}^S g_s E_s \exp(+j\alpha_s d) = \sum_{m=1}^N a_m e_m \exp(-j\beta_m d) \quad \text{at } z = d \quad (2)$$

b_n and c_n are the complex amplitude of the nth mode of the incident and reflected fields in region I, f_s and g_s are the complex amplitude of the sth mode of incident and reflected fields in region II and a_m is the complex amplitude of the mth mode region III. β_m is the propagation constant for the mth mode in regions I and III and β_s is the propagation constant for the sth mode in region II. e_n are the eigen functions of the electric field in regions I and III, and E_s are the eigen functions in region II. N denotes the total number of guided modes in

regions I and III and S the total number of guided modes in region II. The expressions for the magnetic fields are similar to the above equations. The simultaneous solution of these sets of equations yields the expression for the output modal amplitudes, a_m , in terms of the input modal amplitudes, b_n and c_n , and changes in boundary conditions in region II. The details of this theoretical analysis is to be published soon.

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION AND RESULTS

The testing set-up designed for the detection of modal power, coupled with a computerized data acquisition system is shown in Fig. 2. It consists of (i) a modal launcher, which is designed to launch a particular modal structure into the optical fiber, (ii) a high-sensitivity, high-resolution CCD camera, which is used as a modal analyzer to provide a live image of the far-field pattern at the fiber output, (iii) the modal perturber, which is used to apply quantified stresses either to the optical fiber directly or the fiber embedded in a smart structure and (iv) a computerized image processing system.

The light launching angle used during this experimental investigation was about 8° off-axis, and the fiber used was an optical grade sapphire fiber of approximate core diameter $300 \mu\text{m}$. This launching condition was used to excite higher order modes which are more sensitive to external perturbations than lower order modes. Results obtained by using the spatial modulation technique on an optical grade sapphire fiber, are shown in figures 3-6. The figures show the 2-D far-field pattern recorded at the fiber output. In addition, the figures also show the normalized output intensity profile of the far-field pattern as a function of the scanning angle. The first of these figures (Fig. 3) shows the 2-D image and the horizontal intensity profile, before any stress was applied. This shows that the optical intensity for the lowest order modes (on axis modes) is almost zero, and most of the power is concentrated at an angle equal to the excitation angle.

When a transverse compression load of 0.212 kg was applied to the optical fiber (the interaction length was about a centimeter) placed on a steel platform, there was a change in the modal power distribution at the exit of the fiber as shown by Fig. 4. The applied stress causes an intermodal coupling, leading to transfer of power from higher to lower order modes, thus broadening the light intensity toward smaller angles. As the applied load was increased to 0.803 kg, considerable rearrangement of modal power was seen, as shown by Fig. 5. This shows that more power has been shifted from the periphery to the center of the core. Fig. 6 shows the output far-field pattern when the load was increased to 2.285 kg, where the light intensity at the center has reached a maximum. Figures 3-6 show that the increase in intensity at the center of the fiber can be correlated to the compression load applied to the fiber.

This work was directed toward experimental investigation of modal power variation in optical grade sapphire fibers under various loading conditions. Based on the results obtained from far-field patterns such as figures 3-6 a simple relation was drawn for the on-axis intensity of the far-field pattern as a function of the applied load. The result is a smooth variation in optical intensity at the center of the fiber, induced by the applied stress, as shown in Fig. 7. Based on this correlation a direct and cost effective methodology to apply this technique in practice, is to replace the CCD camera by a single photodetector positioned on the fiber axis to collect power only from the lower order modes.

CONCLUSION

The combination of spatial modulation with multimode sapphire fibers appears to be an attractive methodology for the development of optical sensors for very high temperature applications. The results presented in this paper show that the spatial modulation technique is a sensitive and cost effective methodology that can be exploited for using multimode sapphire optical fibers in sensor applications. Multimode sapphire fibers can be employed as intrinsic or extrinsic sensors for on-line monitoring of ceramic composites and other materials in high temperature environment.

REFERENCES

1. E. D. Jungbluth, Sapphire Fiber Sensors Survive 1600°C , Laser Focus World, Vol. 28, 18-19 (June 92).

Figure 3. The 2-D image and the optical intensity profile of the fiber far-field pattern for scanning angles from -20° to $+20^\circ$, before the load was applied.

Figure 4. The 2-D image and the optical intensity profile of the fiber far-field pattern for scanning angles from -20° to $+20^\circ$, under 0.212 kg applied load.

Figure 5. The 2-D image and the optical intensity profile of the fiber far-field pattern for scanning angles from -20° to $+20^{\circ}$, under 0.803 kg applied load.

Figure 6. The 2-D image and the optical intensity profile of the fiber far-field pattern for scanning angles from -20° to $+20^{\circ}$, under 2.283 kg applied load.

Figure 7. The normalized optical intensity measured at the center of the far-field pattern vs the applied transverse load.

